

ACTION OF ACIDIC REAGENTS ON ETHYL α -METHYL- α -URETHANYL- β -PHENYLPROPIONATE

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Action of phosphorus oxychloride on ethyl α -methyl- α -urethanyl- β -phenylpropionate leads to the formation of a 2:5-diketopiperazine derivative (III).

Few attempts have been made to cyclise appropriate urethane derivatives to *isoquinolines*. Dey and Parikshit (*Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1945, 11, 37) subjected methyl N-3:4 methylenedioxystryrylcarbamate to the action of various acidic reagents, such as alcoholic hydrogen chloride or phosphorus oxychloride in toluene or hot sulphuric acid, and in each case a neutral nitrogen-free compound was obtained, recently characterised as 2:3-methylenedioxy-6-(3:4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-naphthalene by Gopinath *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1144). However, the dihydro derivative of the above urethane has been found by Dey and Parikshit (*loc. cit.*) to yield, when treated with phosphorus oxychloride, the corresponding 1-hydroxy-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline.

It has been considered to be of interest to synthesise ethyl α -methyl- α -urethanyl- β -phenylpropionate and subject it to the action of various acidic reagents, so that 1-hydroxy-3-methyl-3-carbethoxy-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline, if obtained, could be easily converted into 3-methyl-3-carbethoxy-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline. The latter *isoquinoline* derivative would constitute a suitable agent for hydrolysis and decarboxylation and for testing whether decarboxylation is followed by dehydrogenation or not. A study of this aspect has been prompted by a previous observation (Ghosh and Dutta, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 17, 755) that, when (α -acetamido- β -phenyl)-ethylmethyl ketone or β -phenyl-substituted analogues are treated with acidic reagents, 1-methylisoquinoline derivatives are formed, the process involving cyclodehydration, deacetylation and dehydrogenation, the exact sequence of which is not clear.

α -Methyl- α -amino- β -phenylpropionic acid (Ghosh, Bhattacharyya and Datta, *ibid.*, 1957, 34, 417) has been conveniently esterified in presence of dry hydrochloric acid gas and the ethyl ester (I), generated from the ester hydrochloride, has been condensed with ethyl chloroformate in an inert solvent to furnish ethyl α -methyl- α -urethanyl- β -phenylpropionate (II). Action of a mixture of phosphorus oxychloride and polyphosphoric acid (cf. Snyder and Werber, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2962) on (II) has furnished (I) as the main product (*vide Experimental*). However, when (II) is treated with phosphorus oxychloride, a neutral compound, devoid of any ketonic property, has been isolated. On hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid this affords α -methyl- α -amino- β -phenylpropionic acid. These properties dispense with the structure (IV) and can be accommodated by the structure (III: R=CO₂Et), also supported by figures on

analyses and molecular weight determination. With hydrazine hydrate, and with semicarbazide hydrochloride in presence of sodium acetate, (III: R=CO-NH-NH₂) and (III: R=CO-NH-NH-CO-NH₂) are respectively formed.

The formation of the 2:5-diketopiperazine derivative (III), effected by the interaction of two molecules of (II), is reminiscent of the synthesis of proline anhydride (tricyclic 2:5-diketopiperazine) from proline ester (Kapfhammer and Matthes, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1934, 223, 43). In this connection reference is also made to the treatment of α -benzamidophenylacetic acid with acetic anhydride, when a compound considered to be 1:4-dibenzoyl-3:6-diphenyl-2:5-diketopiperazine is formed ("The Chemistry of Penicillin" Princeton Univ. Press, 1949, p. 768).

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl α -Methyl- α -amino- β -phenylpropionate (I).—A mixture of α -methyl- α -amino- β -phenylpropionic acid (15 g.) and anhydrous ethanol (150 g.), saturated with dry HCl gas, was allowed to stand at 0° for 24 hours and then heated under reflux for 8 hours. After removal of ethanol under reduced pressure the residue was treated with cold water, basified with sodium bicarbonate and extracted with benzene. Removal of benzene furnished the crude ester which distilled at 152-54°/8-10 mm to yield a colorless liquid (13.5 g.). (Found: N, 6.48. C₁₂H₁₇O₂N requires N, 6.76%)

Ethyl α -Methyl- α -urethanyl- β -phenylpropionate (II).—To a solution of the compound (I, 58 g.) in anhydrous benzene (150 c.c.) a solution of ethyl chloroformate (15.2 g.) in anhydrous benzene (50 c.c.) was added and the mixture was refluxed for about 5 hours, cooled and shaken with water thoroughly. The benzene layer was removed and dried. Removal of benzene left a residue which distilled at 198-200°/8-10 mm to furnish the urethane as a colorless, heavy liquid (36 g.). (Found: N, 4.66. C₁₅H₂₁O₄N requires N, 5.02%). The aqueous layer, on basification with sodium bicarbonate, yielded the compound (I, 25 g.).

Action of a mixture of POCl₃ and Polyphosphoric Acid on (II).—In a flask protected from moisture P₂O₅ (133 g.) was treated with orthophosphoric acid (88%, 86 c.c.)

and the mixture heated on a steam-bath for 2 hours with occasional shaking (cf. Gilmore and Horton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 1411). To this syrupy mass, when cooled, the compound (II, 21 g.) and POCl_3 (27 c.c.) were added and the mixture gradually heated to 125° under reflux and maintained at that temperature for 8 hours. The mixture was then cooled and poured into ice water. The aqueous solution was basified with ammonium hydroxide and the mixture extracted several times with ether. The ethereal extract, after removal of ether, left a residue which was somewhat purified by $\text{HCl-NH}_4\text{OH}$ treatment and was obtained as a thick red liquid (2.8 g.). A sample of this liquid furnished in benzene solution a *picrate*, which was crystallised from ethanol several times till it attained the m. p. $172-73^\circ$, unaltered by further crystallisation. (Found: C, 49.01; H, 4.66; N, 13.10. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7\text{N}_3$ requires C, 49.54; H, 4.58; N, 12.84%). This has been identified to be the *picrate* of the compound (I) by a mixed m.p.

A sample of the above basic liquid was treated with 8% NaOH solution at room temperature with occasional shaking for 1 hour when a major portion went into solution, leaving a small quantity of the liquid which resisted hydrolysis under such condition. The latter was extracted with ether. From the alkaline solution α -methyl- α -amino- β -phenylpropionic acid was isolated by a procedure recorded previously (Ghosh *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). The ethereal extract furnished a small quantity of basic liquid, which gave a *picrate* as a gummy substance, defying attempts for purification. The *chloroplatinate* was also obtained as a pasty mass, which solidified on long standing and melted indefinitely at the range of $194-202^\circ$. This also could not be purified and characterised.

Action of POCl_3 on (II): Formation of 1:4-Dicarbethoxy-3:6-dimethyl-3:6-dibenzyl-2:5-diketopiperazine (III: R = CO_2Et).—A mixture of (II, 23.6 g.) and POCl_3 (32 c.c.) was heated under reflux in an oil-bath, the temperature of which was raised to 90° during 30 minutes. During next 20 minutes the temperature was raised to 108° when a gentle refluxing started. After 10 minutes the bath-temperature was taken slowly to 120° and maintained at that range for 6 hours. After removal of the excess of POCl_3 by distillation at $50-60^\circ$ under reduced pressure, the mass was cooled, treated with ice-water and then extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution (2%) and then with water and dried (sodium sulphate). Removal of ether left a colorless, mobile liquid (9.5 g.), which distilled at $158-60^\circ/9-10$ mm. (Found: C, 67.32; H, 6.48; N, 5.93. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6\text{N}_2$ requires C, 66.95; H, 6.43; N, 6.01%). It is insoluble in cold dilute alkali and in dilute hydrochloric acid.

The *dihydrazide* (III: R = CO-NH-NH_2) was obtained by heating for 30 minutes under reflux an ethanolic solution of (III: R = CO_2Et ; 2.5 g.), to which hydrazine hydrate (1.5 c.c., 46%) was added. It was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. $232-33^\circ$. (Found: N, 18.84. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires N, 19.18%).

The compound (III: R = CO-NH-NH-CO-NH_2) was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. $200-202^\circ$. [Found: N, 20.91; M.W. (Rast), 537. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_6\text{N}_6$ requires N, 21.37%; M.W., 524].

Hydrolysis of (III : R = CO₂Et).—The compound (III : R = CO₂Et ; 6 g.) was heated under reflux with HCl (conc., 30 c.c.) for 8 hours. The solution was evaporated to dryness and the solid obtained was extracted with anhydrous ethanol. The ethanolic solution was concentrated and treated with pyridine till neutral to Congo red. The precipitated solid was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless rectangular plates, m.p. 263-64°, and this was identified to be α -methyl- α -amino- β -phenylpropionic acid by a mixed m.p. with an authentic sample (Ghosh *et al.*, *loc.cit.*).

The authors are grateful to Dr. U. P. Basu, Director of the Institute, for his continued interest.

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Received September 16, 1957.